

Control of leaf blast of rice by Kasumin

M. H. Ashrafuzzaman, professor of plant pathology, Agricultural University, Mymensingh, Bangladesh; and M. A. Rob, plant protection inspector, Jessore, Bangladesh

With the introduction of high yielding varieties, blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* has become a minor disease in Bangladesh. But under highly favorable conditions, it is often serious.

The use of resistant varieties is undoubtedly the most economical method of disease control, but chemicals must be used until susceptible varieties are replaced. A field trial of the antibiotic Kasumin was conducted at Jessore in August 1976 during the kharif season. The variety BR 2 (Mala) was sprayed with Kasumin at 1.12 kg/ha when leafblast symptoms occurred at maximum tillering stage. Three applications were made at 7-day intervals. Twenty days after the last application, 25 leaf samples were

randomly collected from a 0.83 sq-m area with and without treatment, and the percentage of leaf infection was determined.

Kasumin reduced leaf infection from 34.3% to 3.3% in the nontreated observation: 1,222 of 3,555 leaves examined were infected. In the treated samples, 130 of the 3,905 leaves examined were infected. Because of its antibiotic property, Kasumin may be preferred to other fungicides now available in Bangladesh.

Integrated control of rice pests in farmers' fields in Thailand

Somkid Disthaporn, head, Rice Diseases Branch, Plant Pathology Division; Praphas Weerapat, head, Rice Pest and Disease Resistance Branch, Rice Division; and Prakob Leuamsang, head, Rice Insects Branch, Entomology and Zoology Division, Bangkok, Thailand

An integrated program of pest control was conducted in 1976 in areas of about 0.8 – 1.92 ha in North, Northeast,

Central, and South Thailand to determine yield of various rice varieties when insecticides, fungicides, and fertilizers were applied at recommended rates. Results serve as basic information for a larger integrated control program supported by a group of farmers. Materials and methods used were the same in every region: rice seeds were treated with mancozeb (3 gm/kg seed). Carbofuran was applied at 31.25 kg/ha, and MIPC W.P. at 25 g/20 liters of water. The insecticides were applied to the

seedbeds to eliminate green leafhoppers (*Nephotettix* sp.), vectors of yellow orange leaf virus in regions where the disease causes severe damage.

Information from regional plots is summarized (see table). Results for the regions follow:

1. North: RD9, a nonglutinous variety, was moderately resistant (3.6% damage) to the gall midge *Puchydiplosis oryzae*. Local glutinous varieties LL and NSPT had 14.5% and 35.1% damage, respectively. Although RD9 is fertilizer

Some results from plots for integrated control of rice pests in Thailand, 1976.

Variety	Pest damage (%) ^a		Cost (US\$/ha)			Yield (t/ha)	Income (US\$/ha)	Net income (US\$/ha)
	BLB disease	Insects	Chemical	Fertilizer	Cultural and labor			
<i>North: Chiangrai</i>								
RD9*	17	GM 3.6	43.75	35.63	144	3.7	461	238
Lai Luang	30	GM 14.5	43.75	35.63	144	2.9	367	144
Lai Luang	30	GM 20.0	0.00	0.00	144	2.8	352	208
Niaw San Pahtawng*	30	GM 35.1	43.15	35.63	144	2.2	281	58
<i>Northeast: Khon Khan</i>								
RD5*	1	0	0.67	21.81	105	7.4	688	561
RD7*	1	0	0.67	21.81	105	6.9	642	514
Khi-Tom-Yai	15	0	5.80	21.81	105	4.5	307	174
Khi-Tom-Yai	30	SB 0.5	0.67	0.00	105	3.6	241	135
<i>Central: Chacheongsao</i>								
RD7*	0.5	0	5.69	23.75	157	2.3	289	102
RD9*	0.5	0	5.69	23.75	157	3.2	398	212
Khao Khao	0.5	0	5.69	23.75	157	2.9	363	176
<i>South: Phatalung</i>								
BKN 6402-352	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	2.9	294	99
NPY132*	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	3.6	263	68
PN43*	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	2.1	209	14
Lon Krok	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	2.1	211	16
Khai Mod Rin	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	1.8	178	- 17

^a BLB = bacterial leaf blight; GM = gall midge; SB = stem borer, * = government-recommended variety.

responsive and high yielding, it is not popular with farmers. Most farmers in the region own small farms and grow glutinous rice yearly for family consumption. Few own enough land to grow RD9 for trade.

2. Northeast: RD5 and RD7 are high yielding, resistant to diseases and insects, and responsive to fertilizers. Selection of

the proper rice variety, planting date, seedbed location, and pest and disease control in the seedbed gave high production and other benefits.

3. Central: yellow orange leaf disease and brown planthopper are the major problems. Carbofuran (3%) applied once in the seedbed at the rate of 3 1.25 kg/ha was effective.

4. South: The pest and disease levels were comparable in plots planted to the government-recommended varieties (BKN 6402-352, NPY 132, and PN43) and to local varieties (LK and KMR). Yields were similar, but the recommended varieties were more profitable than the local ones. \mathbb{W}

Control of rice blast by tricyclazole 75W.P.

W. H. Tsai, plant pathologist, Chia-yi Agricultural Experiment Station, Chia-yi, Taiwan

On the first crop of 1977, the systemic fungicide Tricyclazole 75 W.P. was tested for control of rice blast on the variety Taiwan 5 in the field. Two popular rice blast fungicides, Hinosan 50 E.C. and Kitazin-p 48 E.C., were used as control.

Tricyclazole 75 W.P. was applied as a soil drench at the seedling stage 1 day before transplanting by machine. The second foliar application was made at 2 days before heading. The two other fungicides were applied twice as foliar application for leaf blast control and twice more for neck blast control.

Tricyclazole 75 W.P. at the rates of 2 and 3 g/flat as a soil drench and at 0.4 kg/ha as a foliar treatment provided excellent control of leaf and neck blast, similar to that by Hinosan (see table). \mathbb{W}

Control of rice blast by Tricyclazole 75 W.P.^a, Chia-yi, Taiwan.

Treatment	Rate of flat ^b application	foliar applications ^c (no.)		Disease incidence		Yield (t/ha)
		Leaf blast	Neck blast	Leaf blast (70)	Neck blast (%)	
Tricyclazole 15 W.P.	2 g/flat	0	1	11.4 ab	1.2 a	5.1 ab
Tricyclazole 15 W.P.	3 g/flat	0	1	11.5 ab	0.7 a	5.5 a
Hinosan 50 E.C.	0	2	2	8.4 a	2.0 a	5.2 a
Kitazin-p 48 E.C.	0	2	2	20.3 b	6.1 b	4.6 bc
Untreated control	0	0	0	34.5 c	16.4 c	4.2 c

^a Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level.

^b At 1 day before machine transplanting, suspending fungicide in 0.5 liter of water and pouring the suspension uniformly over the soil surface of 28day-old-rice plants growing in a 28- × 58- × 3-cm transplant flat.

^c By hand sprayer: once with tricyclazole (0.4 kg/ha) for neck blast control, twice with Hinosan (1 liter/ha) for leaf blast, and twice with Kitazin-p (1.2 liters/ha) for neck blast.

The effect of certain fungicides on rice sheath rot

R. Mohan and C. L. Subramanian, Plant Pathology Laboratory, Agricultural College, Madurai – 625 104, Tamil Nadu, India

Ten fungicides were tested at 0.1 and 0.2% concentrations against

Acrocyndrium oryzae (since revised as *Sarocladium attenuatum*), the pathogen that causes sheath rot of rice.

Both concentrations of benomyl, carbendazim, edifenphos and mancozeb M45 inhibited the growth of *A. oryzae*, but the 0.2% level was much more effective. \mathbb{W}

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Recent brown planthopper incidence and its implications in Malaysia

G. S. Lim and K. L. Heong, Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute (MARDI), Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

Until recently only sporadic and isolated infestations of planthoppers were observed in Malaysia, although damage was sometimes rather serious. The first incidence, recorded in 1925, was an outbreak of the whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* species in Krian (see table). Another outbreak occurred in late 1929 in Province Wellesley and Krian. Apparently no other major infestation was noted until 1967, when the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and *S. furcifera* seriously attacked and destroyed more than 6,000 ha of rice in Trengganu. Closely following that, hopperburn occurred in a number of rice-growing areas. Within the last few years, similar attacks were again reported, usually for the first time, over smaller and more isolated areas. However, no outbreaks occurred over large areas until 1977, when extensive rice fields in Tanjong Karang were attacked by the brown planthopper. Similar brown planthopper buildups, although much smaller in scale, also occurred in Perak (Langkap, Sungai Manek, Parit, and Krian), Malacca, Negri Sembilan, and Province Wellesley (see table).

The brown planthopper may soon become the major rice pest in Malaysia.